

ORGANIC SOURCE AS A TECHNOLOGICAL OPTION FOR SOIL CARBON SEQUESTRATION

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Abstract

The role of organic matter (SOM) in soil fertility has long been known. The relationship between dark soil and use of organic waste and agricultural production were observed for thousands of years. Recently the study of the humified fraction of soil organic matter (SOM), the humic substances (HS), has received new interest in view of its extremely important role in environmental protection. In humid and hot tropical environments, soil due to the pronounced weathering process resulting in an intense removal of silica and bases by lixiviation, are acids and consequently, have low natural fertility. Humic substances comprise a mixture of colloidal molecules without discrete and defined chemical structure with variable C,N,H,O and S contents and varying size, shape, according to Environmental conditions. The valley (plain area) at the center surrounded by hill chains is 10% only. Manipur has an area of 49.25% forest and 6.65% as occupied by agri -land *i.e.* cultivated land. Manipur has nine different districts namely, Sanapati, Urkhul, Churachandpur, Chandel, Bishnupur, Thoubal, Imphal East, Tamenglong and Imphal West. Out of this nine districts soil samples were collected from seven districts namely Senapati, Churachandpur, Chandel, Imphal East, Thoubal, Imphal West and Bishnupur district. As productivity of soils can be sustained with the use of organics. It has been realized that intervention of organic manures as manurial schedule to maintain the soils health and productivity and more view in conserving soil carbon.

The overall strategy is to increase SOC density, distribution of SOC in the sub-soil, aggregation, and formation of secondary carbonates. The SOC density can be enhanced by increasing C input, main focus to organic source like Vermicompost, Biosource and FYM into the soil and decreasing losses by erosion, mineralization and leaching. A study was conducted to assess the organic matter and content of humic and Fulvic acid in Manipur under different land uses system *viz.* Forest, Terrace and cultivated soil. A composite soil samples from three different land use systems of Manipur were studied in surface soil. The mean pH of forest, terrace and cultivated soil was 4.85, 5.10 and 5.39 and their corresponding percentage organic carbon content were 1.05%, 0.99%, 1.685% respectively. Humic acid, the alkali soluble humic fraction was found highest in forest soil than cultivated and terrace lands. The average value of humic acid content in forest, terrace and cultivated soils were 0.75, 0.35 and 0.57g/10g of soil respectively. Being the soil of Manipur is acidic; fulvic acid content was high in terrace soils. The respective average value of fulvic acid content in forest, terrace and cultivated soils were 1.58, 1.75, 1.59g/10g of soil. Vermicompost, biofertilizers and FYM as an organic source were undertaken to study the effect of organic manures in soil parameters and yield of cabbage (*Brassica oleracea* var. *capitata*) in an acid soil. The organic carbon was 2.55% and the highest yield of cabbage was obtained with the application of Vermicompost at 3 t/ ha with *Azospirillum* (17.89 t/ha), which show significantly superior over FYM. The post harvest organic carbon content of soil was significantly improved with the use of vermicompost.

The increase in organic matter content may be due to addition of organic manure with biosource, which stimulated the growth and activity of microorganism, and also due to better root growth. These observations are in line with the finding of Sudhir and Siddaramappa (1995). The effect was further enhanced by the addition of *Azospirillum* soil @ 4 kg ha⁻¹ resulting in the improvement of root growth and nitrogen fixation which resulted in the improvement of cabbage ball formation and increase the organic matter content (Babhulkar *et al.*, 2000). The available nitrogen content of soil after the harvest of cabbage crops increased significantly over the initial contents. The increase was maximum in the treatment of vermicompost @ 3t/ha with *Azospirillum* (275 kg/ha). It may be due to sufficient supply of nutrients by applied organic sources (Acharya *et al.*, 1988). The increase in available nitrogen content of soil after the harvest of cabbage crop in the treatment vermicompost and *Azospirillum* (275kg/ha) might be ascribed to the fact that the addition of *Azospirillum* along with organic source, which is of rich nutrient content, narrowed the C:N ratio of the organic manures and this enhanced the rate of mineralization resulting in rapid release of nutrient from the organic carbon (Sheeba and Chellamuthu, 1999). The results on the available nitrogen content after cabbage the harvest of indicated that the residual effect irrespective of organic source was enhanced. Similar results were reported by Rao (2003). Significantly highest ball yield (17.89 t/ha) was recorded in treatment of vermicompost @ 3 t/ha with *Azospirillum* which was closely followed with Vermicompost @ 2 t/ha plus *Azospirillum*. Overall yield increased from treatment of vermicompost and FYM with *Azospirillum* (17.89, 13.98 t/ha) compared to single application of *Azospirillum*, vermicompost and FYM (7.73, 10.25, 10.32 t/ha) respectively. The increased cabbage yield in the treatment was attributed to the beneficial effect of combined use of organic manure with biosource (*Azospirillum*), which enhanced the nutrient availability. Through enhanced microbial activity conversion from unavailable to available from and also due to improved physical and bio-chemical conditions. These results are in conformity with the findings of Babhulkar *et al.* (2000).

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